

About Interest of Credits With Public Data and Regional Disparities

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Abstract

Google Trends can be a valuable tool in analysing credit interest in the Republic of Armenia when there is a lack of available data. This paper presents some stylized facts about the geography of financial disparities in the country and utilizes Google Trends data to analysing credit trends, comparing it with actual credit data. Additionally, this paper contributes a novel approach of analyzing top and rising queries related to credit in Armenian, as well as examining the multilingual differences in the use of Latin alphabet and searching in English or Russian.

Utilizing Google searches as a data source offers a unique perspective, as it allows us to gather information from individuals who are actively searching for credit-related information on the internet due to the growing popularity of internet and mobile banking. This approach eliminates the need for traditional surveys and provides insights into the interest for credit in Armenia.

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Keywords: google trend, credits, online credits, finance, Republic of Armenia.

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Non-technical summary

This study utilizes Google Trends data to assess credit interests in the Republic of Armenia. It aims to investigate regional disparities in credit-related search activities and explores the influence of language and alphabet preferences on these trends. The research highlights Google Trends data's potential for accurately forecasting credit interest in Armenia, offering insights into credit-related queries and their implications for future investigations. It also establishes a connection between people's linguistic choices in searches and their economic behavior. By examining variations in search patterns, the study focuses on language differences in searching. Figures within the study illustrate how language and alphabet preferences shape search trends, particularly for keywords like 'credit' and 'online credit.' Additionally, it reveals regional disparities in credit searches across Armenia, with the capital city, Yerevan, displaying the highest interest. Various factors, such as the cost of living, the presence of financial institutions, financial literacy, and cultural attitudes, may contribute to these regional distinctions.

In conclusion, this study emphasizes the importance of considering language differences in searches and understanding regional variations in credit-related searches within Armenia. It recognizes the complex nature of these disparities and suggests that a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities within the Armenian financial system can be gained through the examination of these variations. The study's results indicate the potential for accurately assessing credit interests in Armenia using this data source, while also revealing valuable insights from top and emerging credit-related queries that can inform future research. The words individuals choose for credit searches and other financial activities serve as indicators of their forthcoming economic actions.

1. Introduction

How can Google Trends data be used for measuring credit demand? Credit analysis is an important issue in financial systems and the real economy.

In January 2021, there were 2.02 million internet users in Armenia. The number of internet users in Armenia increased by 107 thousand (a +5.6% change) between 2020 and 2021. Internet penetration in Armenia stood at 68.2% in January 2021. I propose using Google data as a proxy for measuring people's interest in credit.

According to World Bank survey data ([Raja and Malumyan \(2020\)](#)), 96 percent of households in Armenia have access to the internet, and 3G service is widely available, covering about 90 percent of the country (excluding mostly unpopulated mountainous regions).

There is a wide array of alternative measures of economic activity outside of official statistics that provide insights into the economic climate. Some of these indicators are more timely than official statistics and can be used to predict official time series or ensure the quality of these series.

One valuable source of data is Google Trends, which offers insights into the volume of search terms entered into the Google search engine. This data source provides a clear picture of what both consumers and businesses are searching for on the internet. According to [Ayoubkhani \(2012\)](#), The Office for National Statistics (ONS) regularly publishes official statistics on the annual internet access of individuals in the UK. These statistics show a consistent increase, with 0.9 million more individuals accessing the internet in 2009 compared to 2008, and 5 million more in 2009 compared to 2006. This continuous growth in internet access enhances the potential of internet search data as an indicator of individuals' economic intentions.

Google offers three valuable data sources for social scientists: Google Trends, Google Correlate, and Google Consumer Surveys ([Stephens-Davidowitz and Varian \(2014\)](#)). Google

Trends data represent the relative popularity of search terms, as mentioned by various studies ([Jun et al. \(2018\)](#), [Xu and Berkely \(2014\)](#), [Huang et al. \(2020\)](#), [Tarkhamtham et al. \(2021\)](#)). This feature prevents situations where regions with the highest search volume would always be ranked the highest. Naturally, this normalization also implies that regions with the same search interest for a term do not necessarily have the same total search volumes, according to [Choi and Varian \(2012\)](#). Economists, investors, and journalists closely monitor monthly government data releases on economic conditions. Unfortunately, these reports come with a lag, as data for a given month is usually released about halfway through the next month and revised several months later ([Choi and Varian \(2012\)](#)).

Google Trends provides daily and weekly reports on the volume of queries related to various industries. [Choi and Varian \(2012\)](#) hypothesizes that this query data may be correlated with the current level of economic activity in specific industries and thus may help predict subsequent data releases. In recent times, practitioners widely use large sets of alternative data for short-term macroeconomic forecasting, including web scraped data, Google data (Trends, Correlate, or Search), scanner data, or satellite data.

[Ferrara and Simoni \(2020\)](#) focuses on research questions related to alternative datasets: (A) when such data improve nowcasting accuracy, and (B) whether they are useful even after controlling for official variables typically used by forecasters, such as opinion surveys or production data. [Ferrara and Simoni \(2020\)](#) also addresses the unique structure of Google Search Data (GSD) and suggests an econometric approach for nowcasting macroeconomic indicators using GSD alongside official data when available.

In the context of Armenia, Google searches for the term "banking" have shown a significant increase between 2020 and 2022. This suggests that individuals in Armenia are more inclined to use search engines to find information about financial services. Several factors may explain this surge.

One possibility is that the COVID-19 pandemic has heightened the demand for financial services. The pandemic led to income reductions for many people, resulting in a greater need for loans and financial assistance. As a consequence, people may have turned to search engines to find information about these services.

Another explanation could be the economic crisis in Armenia, which has led to an increased demand for financial services. Recent years have witnessed economic struggles, resulting in higher unemployment and poverty rates. Individuals facing financial challenges may resort to search engines to explore options like loans, savings accounts, and other financial products.

Additionally, the popularity of online banking might be contributing to the rise in Google searches for the term "bank." In recent years, more individuals have been managing their finances over the internet. This trend is expected to continue, potentially leading to further increases in searches for "banking."

Several other factors may have contributed to this trend, including the introduction of new financial products and the growing use of smartphones and other mobile devices in Armenia.

Overall, the increase in Google searches for "banking" in Armenia indicates a growing interest in financial services among the population.

Next section is about literature review. The literature review is divided into two parts: the first part focuses on literature about Google Trends analysis, and the second part centers on linguistics literature. Section 3 is about descriptive statistics, specifically different financial activity word searches. Section 4 is titled 'People's Interest by Regions,' which discusses regional disparities in Armenia. Section 5 is about methodology. Section 6 is the discussion and open questions section. Does it hold value to use Google Trends data for research when actual data are available? Section 7 is the summary.

2. Literature review

The literature review is divided into two parts: the first part focuses on literature about Google Trends analysis in economics, while the second part centers on linguistics literature, primarily concentrating on online searching and language switching issues.

2.1. *Google trends*

Medeiros and Pires (2021) reaffirmed the value of internet search data as a potent forecasting tool while also drawing attention to its limitations. These limitations include the absence of actual search volume data and the dynamic nature of Google Trends' index, which evolves continually. The authors pointed out that these features can pose challenges for forecasters when dealing with less frequently searched topics or when analyzing historical data over extended periods. Furthermore, they demonstrated through simulated and real data that enhancing model selection and forecasting accuracy is achievable by aggregating multiple samples with matching specifications.

Jun et al. (2018) conducted a comprehensive and impartial investigation into the impact of public use of Big Data from web searches on research. They delved into the implications of Google Trends in the realm of Big Data utilization and application. To achieve this, they performed a network analysis of 657 research papers that utilized Google Trends, identified key network nodes, and assessed the research directions of representative papers.

According to Cebrián and Domenech (2022), Google Trends (GT) has gained popularity as a data source across a wide spectrum of fields, with its economic applications mainly revolving around forecasting other economic variables, such as tourism demand, unemployment, and sales. The paper scrutinizes the data quality of GT by examining key aspects highlighted in the literature. The analysis exposes notable issues related to the measurement accuracy of GT, which can potentially impact the results derived from GT data and, consequently, the decisions informed by this information. These issues are exemplified through an experiment that repeats GT queries on six different days.

The accuracy dimension pertains to whether the attribute value accurately reflects the true value, considering data-related statistical errors like coverage biases, sampling defects, and non-responses that may influence a source's accuracy.

The popularity of GT-reported searches often serves as an indirect gauge of interest in a particular event or topic. However, it's essential for researchers to be aware of the inherent coverage bias in GT. Firstly, it primarily represents individuals with frequent internet access, and its coverage is still incomplete, especially in specific countries and age groups. Secondly, GT can only capture what is searched for in Google Search, whereas the rising popularity of specialized sites or apps may affect GT's accuracy in measuring interest in certain topics.

[Austin et al. \(2021\)](#) addressed the growing demand for more frequent and timely economic indicators, driven by the pandemic's impact on policymaking. Traditional data collection methods are falling short in delivering these indicators, resulting in a heightened interest in real-time data to detect turning points in economic activity. The paper explores the utilization of data extracted from the Google Places API and Google Trends to develop high-frequency indicators aligned with official statistical concepts and classifications. The authors exemplify this approach with Google data-derived indicators that effectively predict the GDP trajectories of selected countries during the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, they present a methodological toolkit for national compilers aiming to enhance the timeliness and frequency of economic indicators.

The cited literature provides insights into the use of Google Trends data for various research applications, with a focus on its potential and limitations. It highlights the significance of Google Trends as a forecasting tool, emphasizes data quality concerns, and demonstrates how aggregating data samples can enhance forecasting accuracy. Additionally, the literature discusses the impact of Google Trends on research and explores its implications in the context of Big Data utilization. It also delves into the popularity of Google Trends in different fields, especially economics, and raises questions about data quality. The literature underscores the need to consider coverage biases and the evolving digital landscape when utilizing Google Trends data. Lastly, it showcases the application of Google data in developing high-frequency

economic indicators to meet the growing demand for timely and relevant economic insights, especially in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

2.2. Sociolinguistics

[Fu \(2019\)](#) discusses the growing significance of Cross-Language Information Retrieval (CLIR) in the Information Retrieval (IR) research community due to the abundance of online multilingual resources. However, it also highlights the scarcity of research into the "how" and "why" of multilingual search behaviors, particularly regarding how multilingual searchers switch and blend languages in queries to achieve satisfactory results. The study primarily focuses on the intra-sentential code-switching behaviors of Chinese-English bilinguals during online searches. It investigates aspects like scenarios and reasons for code-switching, factors influencing this behavior, query formulation patterns, and the role of current IR systems and search tools in facilitating these information needs. The research methodology involved in-depth semi-structured interviews with 30 participants selected via purposive sampling based on their English proficiency, location, and profession. The study identifies four scenarios and reasons for employing mixed language queries and underscores the significance of linguistic and cultural/social factors in code-switching behaviors. It emphasizes that mixed language queries play a unique role in searches and cannot be replaced by single-language queries or other search features. This research contributes to a deeper theoretical understanding of bilingual users' search strategies and interactions with IR systems and offers insights for designing more effective IR systems and tools for exploring multilingual online resources.

[Rózsa et al. \(2015\)](#) delves into online searching, a fundamental aspect of information behavior for internet users. It typically occurs in the user's native language, but English is often used as a foreign language due to limited content availability in underrepresented languages on the web. The study investigates the behaviors of users who search in English as

a foreign language, shedding light on the challenges faced by non-native English speakers in information retrieval. Qualitative methods, such as focus groups, reveal the problems encountered by foreign language searchers, differences in information-seeking behavior between English and their native language, and suggestions provided by participants for effective searching in English.

Building upon the work of [Bhatt and Bolonyai](#), a bilingual grammar framework is introduced to elucidate the socio-cognitive foundations of code-switching. This framework outlines five general principles that explain instances of code-switching and its underlying reasons, supported by empirical evidence across languages. These sociolinguistic principles act as socio-cognitive constraints on code-switching, manifesting as "local" functions of code-switching, specific instantiations, or their interactions.

[Bokamba \(1989\)](#) critically reviews the syntactic study of code-mixing, particularly emphasizing the paradigm of syntactic constraints. The study challenges the notion of the universal applicability of seven major surface constraints, asserting that universality cannot be substantiated by cross-linguistic data. It underscores the inadequacy of a constraint-oriented approach, advocating for a more comprehensive theory of code-switching and code-mixing, which considers factors like multilinguality degree, language variety usage in context, and sociolinguistic motivations. The study proposes an integrated analysis of structural, psycholinguistic, and sociolinguistic data to achieve a holistic understanding.

In the context of the increasing availability of non-English resources on the web, [Chau et al. \(2007\)](#) explores information-seeking behavior in non-English languages, with a specific focus on the Chinese language. The study analyzes three months of search-query logs from a Chinese-focused search engine, revealing similarities and differences in search behavior compared to English-based search engines. It highlights the use of operators in query formulation and the limited use of unique Chinese characters in search queries, offering valuable insights for

further research in non-English web searching.

[Gardner-Chloros and Edwards \(2004\)](#) challenges underlying assumptions in many 'grammars' of code-switching, questioning assumptions about informal speech description, the role of grammar in speech production processes, the notion of a 'base' language, and the universality and predictability of constraints derived from existing data. The study advocates for shifting the focus from seeking universal, predictive grammatical rules to considering the variability of bilingual grammars, taking into account diverse repertoires and sociolinguistic factors influencing code-switching.

[Heller \(2010\)](#) discusses codeswitching, the phenomenon of using multiple languages within a single communicative event, which has attracted significant attention due to its deviation from the convention of using one language at a time. It emphasizes the functionalist approach, interpreting codeswitching as a strategy that bridges or upholds linguistic boundaries, playing a crucial role in defining social roles, relationships, networks, and boundaries. Codeswitching is instrumental in defining multiple role relationships within interlocutors, relying on shared conventions and a mutual understanding of the communicative resource pool.

In the book by [Myers-Scotton \(1997\)](#), the focus is on intrasentential codeswitching, where two or more languages are used within a single sentence. This work underscores the grammatical theory's significance in understanding codeswitching. The research addresses the structural aspects of alternating between linguistic varieties, introducing a model of morphosyntactic constraints governing codeswitching. The study concludes that these principles have universal applicability, supporting a lexically based language production model and contributing to a grammatical perspective on codeswitching.

Similarly, [Shin \(2010\)](#) explores code-switching within bilingual communities and its connection to social and cultural identities of speakers. The act of switching languages in bilingual discourse often reflects the ethnic identity of speakers. This research investigates

the functions of code-switching in a Korean Sunday school, analyzing codeswitching data comprehensively. It identifies situation-related code-switching and demonstrates how Korean is strategically used in various conversational acts to invoke authority figures and navigate potentially offensive remarks. The study argues that the use of Korean in bilingual discourse indexes Korean ethnic identity, invoking traditional social ideologies of relative status and enhancing solidarity.

In the realm of multilingual search behavior, the literature offers valuable insights into different aspects of language use, information retrieval, and code-switching. [Fu \(2019\)](#) focuses on cross-language information retrieval (CLIR) and highlights the significance of studying how multilingual searchers switch and blend languages in queries. The research methodology involves in-depth interviews, revealing scenarios and reasons for code-switching. It underlines the role of linguistic and cultural factors in these behaviors, emphasizing the unique value of mixed language queries.

On a similar note, [Rózsa et al. \(2015\)](#) explores the challenges faced by non-native English speakers when searching in English as a foreign language. The study employs qualitative methods to uncover differences in information-seeking behavior between English and native languages. It provides valuable insights for improving information retrieval experiences for non-native English speakers.

Additionally, [Bhatt and Bolonyai](#) presents a bilingual grammar framework that elucidates the socio-cognitive foundations of code-switching. The framework introduces five principles that explain code-switching instances and their underlying reasons. The empirical evidence supports these sociolinguistic principles, contributing to a deeper understanding of code-switching across languages.

In the context of code-switching, [Bokamba \(1989\)](#) challenges the universal applicability of syntactic constraints and calls for a more comprehensive theory that considers various

factors, such as language variety usage and sociolinguistic motivations. The study advocates for the integration of structural, psycholinguistic, and sociolinguistic data analysis to gain a comprehensive understanding of code-switching. [Chau et al. \(2007\)](#) delves into information-seeking behavior in non-English languages, particularly focusing on the Chinese language. It offers insights into search behavior and the use of operators in query formulation. This research contributes to understanding non-English web searching.

Moreover, [Gardner-Chloros and Edwards \(2004\)](#) challenges underlying assumptions in the study of code-switching and advocates for a shift from seeking universal, predictive grammatical rules to considering the variability of bilingual grammars. In a broader context, [Heller \(2010\)](#) interprets code-switching as a strategy that bridges or upholds linguistic boundaries, defining social roles and relationships at various levels. The functionalist approach emphasizes the role of codeswitching in social interactions. [Myers-Scotton \(1997\)](#) explores intrasentential code-switching, addressing the structural aspects of alternating between linguistic varieties. The research provides a grammatical perspective on code-switching. Lastly, [Shin \(2010\)](#) investigates code-switching within bilingual communities and its connection to social and cultural identities of speakers, highlighting the functions of code-switching in invoking authority figures and enhancing solidarity.

These studies collectively contribute to a deeper understanding of multilingual behavior, code-switching, and information retrieval, encompassing various languages and contexts.

3. Descriptive statistics

Interest of people in Armenia for credit searches determined also by linguistics. Some people using Armenian alphabet for Armenian words searching, some using Latin alphabet for writhing Armenian words in internet, also people using Russian and English.

The final graph is of particular interest as it depicts the search trends for the word “credit” in Armenian, online credit, and the Armenian word “credit” written in Latin alphabet. These searches in the Republic of Armenia present a compelling avenue for research. Firstly, these distinct search groups are comprised of individuals with differing economic behaviors. Secondly, there is a notable data gap in comprehending the current economic situation, which can be addressed by utilizing open-source data such as Google Trends to gain deeper insights into public interests. Thirdly, such data can facilitate credit nowcasting and forecasting by providing access to real-time data.

As a novel approach, I tried to broaden my search beyond a single keyword, such as “credit”. In Armenia, people use the Armenian alphabet, but some people write Armenian

((a)) Topics: banking

((b)) Queries: banking

Fig. 1. Google trend related queries and topics for banking

words in the Latin alphabet when searching for information online. For instance, “credit” in Armenian is written as “vark” (am). The first figure shows the trend in searches for “credit” in the Latin alphabet (red line) and Armenian alphabet (blue line). The trend is higher for searches in the Latin alphabet and has been increasing during the pandemic year. The second figure displays the trend in searches for “credit” and “online credit”. The trend for “credit” searches is higher at the end of 2020. The third figure shows searches for “credit”(ru) in Russian, with the red line indicating “credit” searches and the blue line representing “online credit” searches. Finally, the fourth figure displays searches for the word “bank” in Armenian, English, and Russian. The trend is higher for searches in English (green line) compared to the other languages.

Fig. 2. Google trends

((a)) 2004-2022

((b)) 2010-2022

Fig. 3. Google trends and credits

((a)) 2015-2022

((b)) 2019-2022

Fig. 4. Google trends and credits

4. People’s interest by regions

The map of Armenia shows that there are significant regional disparities in terms of credit searches for the word "credit." The highest number of searches for the word "credit" is found in the city of Yerevan, which is the capital of Armenia. The lowest number of searches for the word "credit" is found in the southern region of Syunik.

There are a number of possible explanations for these regional disparities. One possibility

is that the cost of living is higher in Yerevan, which may lead to more people needing to take out loans. Another possibility is that there are more financial institutions in Yerevan, which makes it easier for people to access credit.

It is also possible that the regional disparities in credit searches reflect differences in the level of financial literacy. People in Yerevan may be more likely to be aware of the benefits and risks of credit, and they may be more likely to use credit responsibly.

Whatever the explanation, the regional disparities in credit searches in Armenia highlight the importance of financial education. People in all regions of Armenia need to be aware of the benefits and risks of credit, and they need to be able to use credit responsibly.

Here are some additional interesting interpretations about the regional disparities in credit searches in Armenia:

The disparities may reflect differences in the level of economic development. Yerevan is the most economically developed region in Armenia, and it is likely that people in this region have more access to credit and are more likely to use it. The disparities may also reflect differences in the cultural attitudes towards credit.

In some cultures, credit is seen as a sign of wealth and success, while in other cultures, it is seen as a sign of financial insecurity. It is possible that the cultural attitudes towards credit in Yerevan are more positive than in other regions of Armenia.

Finally, the disparities may also reflect differences in the availability of data. It is possible that there are more people in Yerevan who use Google to search for information about credit, while people in other regions may use other sources of information.

Overall, the regional disparities in credit searches in Armenia are a complex issue with no easy answers. However, by understanding these disparities, we can better understand the challenges and opportunities facing the Armenian financial system.

The maps below display Google trends by regions (Fig. 5-Fig. 7). In Fig. 5(a), it shows

and the surrounding regions. First, these regions are home to the majority of the Armenian population, so it is likely that there are simply more people in these regions who are interested in taking out loans. Second, these regions are also home to the most economic activity in Armenia, so there may be more businesses and individuals who need to borrow money to finance their operations.

The lower number of credit searches in the southern and eastern regions of Armenia may be due to a number of factors. These regions are less developed than the central and northern regions, so there may be fewer businesses and individuals who need to borrow money. Additionally, these regions are also home to a larger proportion of the Armenian population who live in rural areas, and rural residents may be less likely to take out loans than urban residents.

Overall, the map shows that there is a high demand for credit in Armenia, particularly in the capital city and the surrounding regions. This suggests that there is a growing economy in Armenia, and that businesses and individuals are increasingly looking to borrow money to finance their activities.

Here are some additional thoughts on the interpretation of the image:

The number of credit searches may not be a perfect indicator of the actual demand for credit. For example, some people may search for the word "credit" without actually intending to take out a loan. However, the map does provide a general overview of the regions where people are most interested in credit. The map does not show the reasons why people are searching for credit. Some people may be searching for credit to finance a new business, while others may be searching for credit to pay for unexpected expenses. The reasons why people are searching for credit can vary depending on the individual and the circumstances. The map is only a snapshot of the demand for credit in Armenia in 2017-2022. It is possible that the demand for credit has changed since then. However, the map provides a useful starting

point for understanding the regional demand for credit in Armenia.

The image shows a map of Armenia with different shades of color representing the number of credit searches per city in 2017-2022. The darker the color, the more credit searches there were in that city.

The map shows that the highest number of credit searches were in the capital city of Yerevan, followed by the cities of Gyumri, Vanadzor, and Kapan. The lowest number of credit searches were in the cities of Berd, Martuni, and Sevan.

There are a few possible explanations for the high number of credit searches in Yerevan and the surrounding cities. First, these cities are home to the majority of the Armenian population, so it is likely that there are simply more people in these cities who are interested in taking out loans. Second, these cities are also home to the most economic activity in Armenia, so there may be more businesses and individuals who need to borrow money to finance their operations.

The lower number of credit searches in the smaller cities and towns of Armenia may be due to a number of factors. These cities and towns are less developed than the larger cities, so there may be fewer businesses and individuals who need to borrow money. Additionally, these cities and towns may also be home to a larger proportion of the Armenian population who live in rural areas, and rural residents may be less likely to take out loans than urban residents.

Overall, the map shows that there is a high demand for credit in Armenia, particularly in the capital city and the surrounding cities. This suggests that there is a growing economy in Armenia, and that businesses and individuals are increasingly looking to borrow money to finance their activities.

Credit searches (2017-2022)

((a)) 2017-2022

Credit searches (2017-2022)

((b)) 2017-2022

Fig. 6. Google trends

"Ասրկ" (arm) searches (2017-2022)

((a)) 2017-2022

"Ասրկ" (arm) searches (2017-2022)

((b)) 2017-2022

Fig. 7. Google trends by regions

((a)) Interest by regions 2018-2022

((b)) Searches by cities 2018-2022

Fig. 8. Google trends, Republic of Armenia

5. Methodology

A Vector autoregressive (VAR) model is useful when one is interested in predicting multiple time series variables using a single model (Hanck et al. (2019)). The vector autoregression (VAR) model extends the idea of univariate autoregression to k time series regressions, where the lagged values of all k series appear as regressors. Put differently, in a VAR model we regress a vector of time series variables on lagged vectors of these variables. As for AR(p) models, the lag order is denoted by p so the VAR(p) model of two variables X_t and Y_t ($k = 2$) is given by the equations

$$Y_t = \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}Y_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_{1p}Y_{t-p} + \gamma_{11}X_{t-1} + \dots + \gamma_{1p}X_{t-p} + u_{1t},$$

$$X_t = \beta_{20} + \beta_{21}Y_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_{2p}Y_{t-p} + \gamma_{21}X_{t-1} + \dots + \gamma_{2p}X_{t-p} + u_{2t}.$$

the structure of VARs also allows to jointly test restrictions across multiple equations.

For instance, it may be of interest to test whether the coefficients on all regressors of the lag p are zero. This corresponds to testing the null that the lag order $p1$ is correct. Large

sample joint normality of the coefficient estimates is convenient because it implies that we may simply use an F -test for this testing problem.

The explicit formula for this test statistic is complex; fortunately, these computations can be easily performed using the R functions I utilize in this paper.

Forecast of series CREDIT

Forecast of series GT_CREDIT

6. Discussion

Does it hold value to use Google Trends data for research when actual data are available?

Yes, it does, for two reasons. Firstly, it allows for the analysis of behavioral aspects and people’s decision-making processes, such as the wording they use when searching for information.

Secondly, it’s worth noting that data that changes on a weekly basis may be more relevant than quarterly or yearly official data, particularly when considering sensitive, time-sensitive behaviors.

The data used for the analysis is Google Trends data spanning from 2018 to 2022. Forecasts indicate that the trend will decrease in 2024, with a notable peak in searches in 2020 due to lockdown measures. It’s also worth mentioning the relative search interest in terms such as ‘mortgage’ (in Armenian: ‘hipotek’) and ‘credit’ (in Armenian: ‘vark’). Google Trends provides valuable insights into these topics.

Fig. 9. Google trends, Republic of Armenia

The decrease in trends can be attributed to two reasons. First, the market is saturated, meaning it has reached its maximum capacity. Second, it may be due to reduced active usage

of search tools, as people might find the information they need during their initial search and do not conduct additional searches.

Novelty for analysis, which could be used for research in other countries, is the potential for linguistically diverse searches to provide a more accurate understanding of economic behavior and markets.

Figure 10 (a) below displays searches for "credit," "vark," "kredit," "vark" (in the Armenian alphabet), with the black line representing the average search volume (*credit_ev*) for these four words. Figure 10 (b) shows the forecast for *credit_ev*.

((a)) Interest by regions 2018-2022

((b)) Searches by regions 2018-2022

Fig. 10. Google trends, Republic of Armenia

"vosku," and "global." This suggests that people in Armenia have diverse interests in credit, ranging from financing businesses to making substantial purchases and covering unexpected expenses. Searches related to "bank" are connected with words like "converse," "ararat," and "id." This implies that people in Armenia have varied motivations for engaging with banks, such as opening accounts, depositing money, and withdrawing funds. The words "hay" and "business" are closely linked on the right side of the graph, indicating a strong interest in business and entrepreneurship among the Armenian population. They may be searching for information on how to start, manage, or secure financing for a business.

In summary, the graph illustrates the broad spectrum of topics related to money, finance, business, and entrepreneurship that pique the interest of people in Armenia. This suggests that the Armenian economy is thriving, and individuals are becoming increasingly financially savvy.

Additional considerations for interpreting the graph:

The graph provides a snapshot of the most popular queries in Armenia as of September 2023. Popularity may have changed since the graph's creation.

The graph doesn't reveal the specific motivations behind these queries. People may seek information on these topics for personal or business reasons.

The graph measures query popularity but doesn't assess the quality of available information on these topics.

Google Trends: top queries (AM)

7. Summary

Using Google Trends for credit forecasting offers a novel and promising approach, as demonstrated in recent studies. It's important to acknowledge its limitations, though. While Google Trends provides valuable insights into the search behavior of individuals in specific regions, it doesn't offer a comprehensive view of credit activity or creditworthiness. For instance, it may not account for individuals who don't use the internet to seek financial information or those who use alternative financial services that aren't easily tracked online.

Nonetheless, combining descriptive statistics with Google Trends data can provide valuable information about regional disparities in credit behavior. Analyzing the search volume for credit-related terms in different regions allows researchers to gain insights into variations in credit activity and demand throughout the Republic of Armenia. These insights can inform policy decisions and support the development of targeted interventions to address disparities in credit access and usage.

Looking ahead, the future potential of Google Trends in credit forecasting may be enhanced by incorporating additional variables directly related to credit activity. For example, integrating data on credit scores, loan applications, and default rates could offer a more nuanced understanding of credit behavior and enable more accurate credit forecasting. Furthermore, applying machine learning techniques to analyze both Google Trends data and traditional credit data could lead to more robust credit forecasting models.

In conclusion, while Google Trends shows promise for credit forecasting, it should complement other data sources while considering its limitations. The inclusion of supplementary variables and the application of machine learning techniques can enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of credit forecasting using Google Trends, ultimately contributing to the development of more effective credit policies and interventions.

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